

Mental Well-being of Patients during Coronavirus Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

On 31st January 2020 the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the outbreak of a new coronavirus disease, COVID-19, to be a Public Health Emergency of International Concern and In March 2020, WHO made the assessment that COVID-19 can be characterized as a pandemic. Various international organizations and governments are taking required actions to prevent the spread of coronavirus. Pandemic is having serious implications on physical as well as mental health of the person. Before the coronavirus people were struggling from mental issue and the coronavirus has made the things bad to worse. COVID-19 which is caused by novel coronavirus is raising concerns of increase in anxiety, depression and stress and it is also raising apprehension of widespread panic. The quarantine and isolation measures have played an important role in preventing the spread of virus but it has negatively affected the mental health of the human being. The pandemic is having adverse psychological consequences which are impacting the mental health of the individual and as mental health plays an important role in working of the human being, so mental problems or issues will definitely impact their working manner and capacity in an adverse manner. Therefore we can say that COVID-19 will have rippling effects, especially based on current public reactions. In our survey also we have found that people who are tested positive are suffering from anxiety, depression and stress etc and they do yoga and meditation to improve their mental health. Through this survey we have tried to find out that which age group is more vulnerable to the pandemic, whether their mental health get affected during quarantine, whether they become addictive of smart phone etc. during quarantine. The survey was designed to find out the implications of COVID-19 on mental health of persons.

Keywords: COVID-19; Mental health; Public health emergency; Quarantine

INTRODUCTION

In the month of March coronavirus pandemic had heavily affected more than 190 countries in the world. Each and every country had taken various measures such as lockdown, social distancing, social isolation, border-closure and quarantine etc. All the economic, social, political and religious activities were restricted by governments [1]. No-body was allowed to roam around the streets, roads, public places etc. Besides taking all these steps 'Covid' was spreading rapidly all over the world and it was engulfing every human being regardless of their age, sex or religion but covid had taught us that we all are equal in the eyes of nature; we should live together with love and affection, we

should protect the other's life and take care our elders. It teaches us the importance of each and everything in our life and in particular the role played by family in our life. Due to this competitive era we all were fighting with each other, concerned only about monetary gains but when this pandemic emerged, we became able to spend some time with our family, learn new things, develop new skills and work on our mental and physical well being. Beside some positives from this pandemic, it was having various negative impacts on our health particularly on our mental health. Before covid number of suicides, cases of depression, stress and anxiety were increasing rapidly and this pandemic has added fuel to the fire [2,3]. Due to the measures taken by governments such as lockdown, quarantine etc. people

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who were living alone were feeling lonely, they were frustrated and were also becoming the victim of depression, anxiety, stress, fear and nervous shock etc. People were consuming more drugs and alcohols and all these things had worsened their mental as well as physical health also. In this difficult time health workers were giving 24/7 hr service, they were having excessive work-load which were affecting their mental health. They were discriminated and treated badly by society, people were afraid of them and thinking that if they came in contact with health-workers and doctors than they also become patient of covid. Therefore people were expelling them from society. All such things deteriorated their mental health. Old people specifically those who were suffering from any disease were at the verge danger. They were not familiar with living in one room, not going outside, wearing mask all time, so their mental condition were also worsened. Most importantly mental health of child got much affected because their schools were closed down, they were not allowed to go outside and play and meet their friends. Children were getting addicted of smart phones and televisions because they were nothing to do other than playing on mobile phones and watching TVs and these electronic devices were very much affecting their mental health. People who were daily earners were not able to earn, not able to food their family and not able to run their household, so they facing economic problems which were encouraging them to commit suicide etc. their mental conditions were also got very much affected by covid. Some of the persons who suffered from COVID-19 were having long-lasting impact of pandemic on their mental health because of isolated and bad treatment from society. Men is a social animal who generally loves to interact with people and make more connection with them but when they set aside from such thing and put in isolation than it becomes very difficult for them and the time which they spent in isolation is going to have long-lasting impact on their mental health. In this way coronavirus pandemic is heavily affecting our mental as well as physical wellbeing.

Therefore it can be said that various strict measures taken by government are playing an important role in curbing the spread of coronavirus pandemic but such measures are also affecting our mental well being. So it is the need of hour to take care of mental wellbeing of each and every person and specifically those who are suffering from coronavirus. Although various government have taken various steps in countering mental problems but this needs to be boost-up and people should work with government to tackle mental issues.

Mental Wellbeing of Patients during Coronavirus Pandemic (Key Concepts):

The basic concepts of this topic is coronavirus pandemic, its implications on our mental health, the age group which is at the verge of getting infected and having severe mental implications, the demographic condition of the region where spread of the coronavirus is high, the increase in cases of anxiety, depression, stress, fear etc. and how these feeling are tackled. Through this paper and survey we have covered all the above mentioned basic concepts in a detailed manner.

METHODOLOGY

The objective of this research paper and survey is to have holistic idea about the impact of coronavirus on mental health of all and particularly those who had tested COVID-19 positive and propose solutions and measures for resolving the mental issues of human beings and ultimately contribute in the fight against covid. It tends to find out the root cause of the problem and solution to it which will ultimately help us to ameliorate the mental condition of patients of coronavirus. This research paper had emphasized on Empirical research methodology, it is used by conducting various surveys, taking opinion from different people of the society. Surveys are also been taken into consideration for collecting relevant data to understand and analyze all important aspects of the topic in a very well-versed manner. We have designed a survey in which total 10 questions are included and in this survey person belonging to age group of below 20, 20-40 and more than 40 have participated. Questions in the survey are included to elicit which age group is more vulnerable to get infected of COVID-19, whether rural or urban population is more vulnerable of infection, what are the implications of COVID-19 on mental health of infected person and how it impact their working capacity [4].

Data analysis and interpretation

In the survey conducted, majority responses were from age group of below 20 which means that the student category is having the majority stake in the survey and the participation of male gender was high the in survey in comparison to female and other gender (Figure1).

Through the survey it was found that persons from urban background are more vulnerable of getting infected with coronavirus. 83.3% of total participant were from urban areas that were tested Covid-19 positive and only 16.7% were from rural area that were tested COVID-19 positive. This data shows that the effect of the pandemic is more in the urban areas in comparison to rural areas. There may be various reasons for the spread of pandemic in urban areas such as the population density of cities is much more in comparison to villages, secondly the life-style and culture of the cities is very much different from rural areas. In rural areas there is less pollution, rural people are having strong immunity, the population is less, the food they eat is healthy a pure and they are not much advanced but the situation in urban areas is just opposite. Pollution level is very high in cities which impact the immunity of the people, so the immunity of urban people is not very

much strong, the population in cities is very high in comparison to rural areas, their food is not nutritious and pure. There may be some other reasons also but mainly above mentioned reasons are prominent for spread of coronavirus in cities (Figure 2).

After analyzing the spread of COVID-19 in urban areas, now we will look at how COVID-19 has impacted mental health of human being. In India government has made guidelines for treatment of COVID-19 patients. Those who are tested COVID-19 positive and are not having severe implication are quarantined or isolated in quarantine centers or put in home isolation. As per data of the survey it was found that people were quarantined between 1 to 3 week. So it becomes very difficult for a person and specially a student to stay alone in a place for such a long period of time because it affects their mental health. During the quarantine period which is normally of 14 days makes the person frustrated as he is unable to walk out or talk to other person face to face. He is not having accompany of any other person so it become very difficult for that person to stay in isolation for 14 days or more than that [5]. We have also seen that at quarantine centers people don't get proper facilities such as food, water, and air etc. it also affects their mental as well as physical health. So in this manner the quarantine which is a great tool for isolating infected person from other persons to curb the spread of coronavirus is adversely affecting the mental health of the persons (Figure 3).

From the survey it was found that 76% of total participants were put in home quarantine and they were treated well. This shows that COVID-19 patients had got full support of their family and other persons. In such a crucial time covid patients need the support of other as they are going through a tough time and had to live in room alone which become very frustrating for them (Figure 4).

Through the survey we found that most of the persons were suffered from some mental issue or problem such as depression, anxiety and stress etc. this shows that how quarantine or home isolation had affected the mental health of the infected persons. The reason behind this was that they were not able to meet and talk with their friends, family members, colleagues etc, so it had affected their mental health. We know that human is a social person who likes to interact with each other and if is not able to interact with others than it becomes very difficult for that person to live a healthy life and same non-interactive situation is arising before the infected persons. Secondly bad thoughts comes in the mind of infected person, negative feelings dominates their thinking which also affects their mental health. Through the survey we found that some people who were tested positive, their whole family was also tested positive. So they were tensed about how they and their family will recover, will everyone be fine etc. and it was also affecting their mental health (Figure 5).

We found that around 64% of total participated people were of opinion that yoga and mediation may help a lot during quarantine. The people were doing exercise, meditation and yoga to remove their stress, depression, anxiety and keep them mentally and physically fit. So we can say that meditation and yoga helps in reducing mental pressure (Figure 6).

In our survey we found that around 1/3rd of covid positive people in our response sheet had not taken the mental effect of the pandemic seriously or we can say that they were not paying attention at mental issue or problems. The reason behind this carelessness was the lack of awareness about the mental health among the public. People generally don't work on their mental health; they do not go to a Psychiatrist for treatment, they don't talk about their depression, anxiety and stress to other person. This carelessness leads to the severe mental implications which some time become the cause of death for persons (Figure 7).

When we asked people whether mental affects their mental health or not, we found that around 68% of the people were of opinion that mental health affect their work, they are not able work properly. This portrays that if people won't pay paramount attention to their mental health, if they won't take precautions than they will not be able to work properly. The survey has also shown that mental health has a direct connection with the work of human being (Figure 8).

Lastly it was identified that during the quarantine period, people become addictive of smart phones. Around 56% people said that they had become addictive of smart phone during quarantine period. During quarantine period they used their smart phones heavily and became addictive of it and heavy access of smart phone has affected their mental health badly. So in this manner mental health of the infected person got affected during quarantine period (Figure 9).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The coronavirus has reached in almost all countries around the world, various governments had taken various steps for restricting the spread of coronavirus pandemic. Lockdown, quarantine, isolation, border-closure and other various policies are made by various government. Through this survey we found that COVID-19 has affected the person from every age group. It has affected the students as well as the old persons. So we can say that each and every one is vulnerable of getting infected of COVID-19. People whether they are undergraduate or post graduate both are getting infected which shows that educated people are not following the covid appropriate behavior and urban population is more likely to get affected by this coronavirus. From the results of the survey we can conclude that quarantine period had adversely affected the mental health of infected persons and through survey it can be said that yoga and meditation may improve the mental health of the COVID-19 Patients [6]. It can also be said that majority people are taking their mental health seriously and are doing exercise, yoga and meditation and taking precautions and keeping them mentally fit as they know that their mental health will affect their work. They know that if they don't pay paramount importance to their mental health and ignore mental problems such as depression, stress, anxiety than their working capacity will also get affected. The conclusion of this survey is that coronavirus has infected young as well as old person and in urban areas infection rate is also high and during quarantine period people had become addictive of smart phone which also affect their mental health and to yoga, meditation and exercise have become an important tool for improving the mental health. Therefore we can conclude that coronavirus which has greatly threatened the life of every single individual in this world is having great impact on mental health of the infected persons and people needs to give paramount importance to their mental health and needs to work on their mental health so that they can work properly and live a better life.

CONCLUSION

Through this survey we found that coronavirus pandemic is having great implications on our mental health. First of all the infected persons and other who are not tested positive but are suffering from psychological consequences of pandemic needs to do meditation, yoga and exercise to control their mind and improve their mental health in such tough situation. Secondly family members and friends and others also needs to support the infected person, they need to treat him well and with due care and needs to motivate the infected person to fight against the COVID-19. Thirdly person needs to be self-restrained; he should not become addictive of smart phones and other electronic gadgets during his quarantine period. Further those person who were quarantined at quarantine centre should be given proper facilities such as nutritious food, pure water etc. Government needs to aware public about telemedicine and other medical facilities so that they can get proper treatment. Such facilities should be made accessible to each and every person and efficacy and effectiveness of such facilities should be increased by government. People suffering from mental issues should use helpline numbers (telemedicine) so that they can consult about their mental problems and get proper advice and solution. One more suggestion will be that people whether they are from rural or urban areas should pay paramount attention to their mental health and in case of any mental health problem such as anxiety, depression, lack of sleep, stress, fear, frustration,

anger depressive disorder etc. they should contact and communicate with psychiatrist; they should not hide their mental illnesses or problems. Lastly we should aware the general public about the mental health and mental illness or problems and their severe implications on our health. So if all people will pay proper attention to their mental health than they will be able to work in an effective and efficient manner and they can live a happy and healthy life.

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